

DIGITAL READING ADVENTURES: DEVELOPING AND EVALUATING VIDEO-BASED MATERIALS FOR READING COMPREHENSION

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ABSTRACT

Exploring the potential of video to enhance reading comprehension in the digital age, this study investigated the effectiveness of video-based digital reading materials for elementary learners in Calinog II District (2023-2024). Employing an ADDIE-informed developmental research design, the study assessed learner needs (Analyze), designed video materials aligned with those needs (Design), developed the materials (Develop), evaluated their impact on learner experiences and comprehension (Implement), and assessed their acceptability by experts (Evaluate). The findings revealed that the video materials, addressing areas like comparison and contrast texts and narrative analysis, fostered positive learner experiences (increased enjoyment and interest) and led to improvements in comprehension and vocabulary development. Additionally, expert evaluation indicated a high level of acceptability for the materials across content, instructional design, and technical aspects. This research suggests that video-based digital reading materials, informed by a structured development process like ADDIE, hold promise as engaging and effective tools for enhancing reading comprehension skills in the digital age.

Keywords: *Digital Material, Reading Comprehension, Instructional Material, ADDIE*

INTRODUCTION

The digital revolution has significantly transformed the educational landscape, demanding innovative approaches to equip learners with essential skills. This transformation has been further accelerated by the recent pandemic, which disrupted traditional classroom learning and propelled the rapid adoption of remote learning models (Celeste, et.al, 2024). While these online and modular formats offer flexibility, they also present unique challenges for students, particularly when it comes to developing strong reading comprehension skills. Reading comprehension, a cornerstone of academic success and lifelong learning (Language and Reading Research Consortium, 2015), necessitates evolving instructional strategies to cater to the changing needs of today's students. Traditional literacy instruction may not fully address the multifaceted demands of the digital age (Smith, 2023).

There is a growing body of research that suggests integrating digital reading materials into classrooms can hold promise for enhancing reading comprehension (e.g., Smith, 2023). These materials offer engaging and interactive experiences that cater to diverse learning styles and preferences (Smith, 2023). By leveraging the interactive features and multimedia elements inherent in digital platforms, educators can design dynamic resources that stimulate critical thinking, promote deeper understanding, and foster a love for reading.

The digital revolution demands innovative approaches to literacy instruction. This study, titled "Designing and Evaluating Video Materials for Enhancing Reading Comprehension Skills," investigates the potential of video-based materials to improve reading comprehension among elementary learners. Employing a developmental research design informed by the ADDIE framework, this study will assess learner comprehension (Analyze), design and develop video materials tailored to identified needs using TPACK principles (Design, Develop), evaluate learner experiences with the materials (Implement), and assess their acceptability by reading experts (Evaluate). By exploring the effectiveness of video-based learning objects, this research aims to inform the development of engaging and effective digital resources for enhancing reading comprehension skills in the digital age.

A developmental research design was employed in this study. The participants were elementary learners from Baje San Julian Elementary School for the school year 2023-2024. The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI) administered at the beginning of the school year served as the baseline assessment for reading comprehension skills.

Investigating the effectiveness of video-based digital reading materials for enhancing reading comprehension can contribute meaningfully to the growing body of research on technology-integrated literacy instruction. This study has the potential to bridge a gap in our understanding of how video specifically impacts reading comprehension skills among elementary learners. The findings can inform theoretical frameworks for multimedia learning and digital literacy development, potentially leading

to the creation of more effective instructional models that cater to the diverse learning needs of the digital generation.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the reading the comprehension skills of the learners as basis for the development and evaluation of video material for the District of Calinog II for the school year 2023-2024.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of reading comprehension of the learners?
2. What digital-based reading materials can be developed based on the result of level reading comprehension?
3. What are the experiences of the learners on the digital-based reading materials?
4. What is the level of acceptability of the digital-based reading materials developed as assessed by the experts.

METHODOLOGY

This developmental study aimed at assessing the reading the comprehension skills of the learners as basis for the development and evaluation of digital reading materials. Specifically, this study made use of ADDIE Model as systematic design framework.

Participants

The research participants were the thirty-eight (38) officially enrolled Grade 6 learners of an Elementary School in the Municipality of Calinog, Iloilo City Philippines for the School Year 2023-2024.

Moreover, other sources of the data were the result of their reading diagnostic test (PHIL-IRRI) at the beginning of the school year. Also, five (5) purposively selected Information Technology experts and four (4) reading teachers evaluated the developed digital reading materials using the adopted evaluation tool of the DepEd LRDMS for non-print instructional materials. Among the thirty-eight (38) learner participants, three (3) were purposively chosen and were interviewed about their experiences of viewing and using the developed digital-based reading material.

Data Gathering Procedure

The collection of data was divided into two stages: (1) Data Gathering (2) Material Development.

Stage 1: Data Gathering. Before the conduct of the study, permission to conduct the research study were secured by the researcher. Upon the approval and securing the

copy of the diagnostic test of the participants, the researchers looked into the result and analyzed the level of the reading comprehension and in what area they perform the lowest. This was used to identify the reading comprehension competency to be improved and the basis of development of video reading material.

Stage 2: Digital-based Reading Material Development. This study employed the ADDIE (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation) Model to develop the instructional material. Furthermore, the following steps were followed:

Analysis. The process began with an analysis of the learners' current situation. This involved assessing their reading comprehension skills using the results of their PHIL-IRI pretest administered at the beginning of the school year. This analysis helped identify knowledge gaps and training needs, which ultimately shaped the learning objectives for the digital materials. This focused on establishing the overall goal of the training itself. In this case, the goal was to develop digital-based reading materials that would enhance the learners' reading comprehension abilities.

Design. With the learning needs and goals identified, the researchers moved to the design phase. Here, they used the insights from the analysis to create a practical plan for the digital materials. This plan encompassed the teaching strategy, delivery methods (e.g., video lectures, interactive exercises), content structure, duration, assessment methods, and learner feedback mechanisms.

Storyboarding or creating a prototype of the materials likely occurred during this stage. This prototype served as a blueprint for the final product and facilitated communication with stakeholders like teachers and subject matter experts. It helped them visualize the value and approach of the training materials.

An initial testing phase using the prototype was crucial for a "sanity check" before extensive development. This testing ensured the feasibility and effectiveness of the planned instructional design.

Development. Guided by the approved design and prototype, the development phase involved creating the actual digital reading materials. This likely included scripting video content, developing interactive exercises, and designing engaging visuals. The core content structure and learning activities were established during the design phase, and here, the focus shifted towards adding detail and polish.

This phase also emphasized the importance of selecting appropriate graphics, colors, and fonts. These elements play a significant role in learner engagement and information retention. Careful consideration was given to the target audience (identified in the analysis phase) to ensure the materials were visually appealing and aligned with their preferences.

Development was likely an iterative process, with content creation followed by testing to identify and rectify basic errors like grammar, spelling, and functionality. This

testing also ensured smooth course navigation, a critical element for preventing learner frustration.

Implementation. Once the digital reading materials were fully developed and tested, they were prepared for implementation and delivery to the learners. The decisions made in the design phase regarding delivery methods came into play here. The videos developed were used by the thirty-eight (38) officially enrolled population of Grade VI elementary learners of Baje San Julian Elementary School for the School Year 2023-2024.

Evaluation. The ADDIE process emphasizes continuous improvement. Evaluation, the final phase, focused on gathering feedback on all aspects of the digital reading materials. This feedback, from learners, instructors, and subject matter experts, would be used to refine and revise the materials for future iterations. The video developed had the following competencies from the MELC's The ICT experts, reading teachers, and selected participants will evaluate the acceptability of the developed digital-based reading materials based on the content, instructional quality, technical quality, presentation and organization, accuracy and up-to-datedness of information.

Data Analysis Procedure

The quantitative data gathered from the reading comprehension results of the learners was subjected to quantitative data analysis. The mean was used to determine the level of reading comprehension of the learners based on the reading diagnostic result (PHIL-IRI). And to determine the experts' evaluation of the digital-based reading materials' acceptability.

The qualitative data gathered on the experiences of the learners in viewing and reading the digital-based reading materials were subjected to thematic analysis. Thematic analysis was used to determine the reading experiences of the purposively selected learners in using the developed digital-based reading materials.

RESULTS

Quantitative Data Analysis

Reading Comprehension Results of the Participants

Table shows the overall reading comprehension scores of the participants using PHIL-IRI. The result showed that the level of reading comprehension of the participants falls under the Instructional Level (M=68.16). This means that learners can generally understand straightforward text and are likely to benefit from instruction and support to improve their reading skills. However, they might struggle with complex text structures or vocabulary, or drawing inferences or making connections between ideas may be challenging. And perhaps, fluency and accuracy in reading might be inconsistent.

A study by Carrasquillo (2013) found that students at the instructional level can decode most words accurately but may struggle with complex text structures or inferences. This can be further supported by the schema theory. This theory suggests that readers activate prior knowledge (schemas) to understand new information. Learners at the instructional level are likely to benefit from activities that build background knowledge and connect text to their existing schemas

Table 2

Level of Reading Comprehension of the Learner Participants

Over-all Score in Reading Comprehension	Description
68.16%	Instructional

PHIL-IRI Oral Reading Level:

Independent	80 – 100%
Instructional	59 – 79%
Frustration	58% and below

Furthermore, using the form annex B2 of PHIL-IRRI revealed the scores of the participants specific areas in reading comprehension. Annex B2 revealed that the Critical Area showed the lowest among the 3 areas in reading comprehension.

Developed Digital Reading Materials

Based on the result of PHIL IRI in table 2, the following competencies in reading were identified and were the basis of developing video reading materials. Since the learners are at the instructional level, the researcher chooses to design and develop digital reading materials in the form of videos. This suggests that incorporating audio and visuals in video lessons might be more engaging and supportive for learners at this level.

The first part of the video presents the competency so that learners will able to know the skills expected to them. Next is motivation questions that will arouse the interest of the learners and will give them idea about the story that they are going to read. Part 2 is the story proper, which the story title is presented and the whole story is read to them. After listening to the story, they will be given a chance to read it. Part 3 is the comprehension questions that will develop learners critical thinking skills. If their score is four-six points, they will get a digital hug but if their score is three and below they will get an advice that they need to watch more digital videos for reading comprehension or replay the video for a better understanding.

Responding appropriately to the messages of the different authentic texts.

Learners encounter a constant stream of information from various sources. These "authentic texts" can be anything from news articles to social media posts, song lyrics to instruction manuals. To interact effectively with these messages, it is crucial to understand not only what they say, but also the underlying purpose.

The first step is identifying the type of text. Is it meant to inform you about current events or provide instructions on how to fix a leaky faucet. Recognizing the text type (informative, persuasive, creative, or instructive) helps you understand the sender's goal. Once the learner can grasp the purpose, they will consider how to respond appropriately. News articles might call for a simple "share" or a comment seeking more details. An advertisement might prompt the learners to research the product further or simply ignore it. For creative texts like poems, learners could analyze the deeper meaning or create your own response piece.

Digital reading material 1 is about news story entitled "Ecology Club Find Golds in Garbage" it is all about the student club named Ecology Club who proposed a project in their school on how to generate a fund coming from the garbage. This material encourages leadership, commitment and resourcefulness as a student leader and teaches learners on how to generate money out of garbage or waste materials. This news story also encourages learners to become a good member of the school community and to give value on proper waste segregation.

Recognizing comparison and contrast text.

Due to the learners' "instructional level" reading comprehension, the researcher developed digital reading materials focused on "recognizing comparison and contrast text." Since learners at this level might struggle with identifying these concepts in written text alone, digital materials (potentially video-based) use visuals and narration to highlight the cues and make them easier to understand. Interactive elements could also be included for additional practice. This approach tailors the learning materials to the specific needs of the learners at the instructional level.

In the digital-based reading material developed, the story is all about the telescope. It tells about the two kinds of the telescopes, its different parts, uses and its importance especially in astronomy. It also compares the reflecting and refracting telescopes when it comes to their lenses and how the importance of light in it. In this story the learners will develop a skill to contrast and compare the telescope, that will leading them to the mastery of the skill. It is in this material where there critical thinking, memory and analyzation skills are enhanced.

Present a Coherent Comprehensive Report on Differing Viewpoints on an Issue.

This competency assesses several skills that can be challenging for students at the instructional level. It requires understanding an issue with multiple perspectives, which can be difficult for learners who struggle with complex text structures. Students need to gather information from various sources and analyze them to understand different viewpoints. This can be challenging for those who might have difficulty navigating complex sources or summarizing key points. Students need to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of each viewpoint, identify potential biases, and consider the bigger picture. Critical thinking skills are often underdeveloped at the instructional level. This competency requires organizing information from multiple sources into a coherent and logical report.

Students at the instructional level might struggle with structuring a complex report with multiple sections and transitions.

The video developed, included a poem where in it tells what happened during pandemic, it is entitled "New Normal". It reminded children about the virus that had hit us last 2019, wherein normal ways become "new normal". It brings many changes, like in our educational system, where modular and online classes are delivered in observance to health protocol. People are required to sanitize themselves, wear mask and maintain social distancing. Online markets even made its way to support the daily needs of the community. This poem showed that despite the challenges we had faced still we worked together and did not let the pandemic make us fall. The poem would be interesting to learners since they have gone to the same situation. The more relationship they can associate with the poem, the more established comprehension they would have enabling them to achieve intended learning outcomes.

Compose Clear and Coherent Sentences Using Coordinating Conjunctions.

This competency might seem straightforward, but for students at the instructional level, it can be more challenging than it appears. Coordinating conjunctions (like "and," "but," "or," "so," "for," "yet") connect clauses within a sentence. Students at the instructional level might struggle with the concept of clauses and how they function together in a sentence.

Using coordinating conjunctions correctly involves proper grammar and punctuation rules. For example, a comma typically precedes a coordinating conjunction joining two independent clauses. Students at the instructional level might have difficulty grasping these nuanced rules.

While some coordinating conjunctions are very common ("and," "but"), others might be less familiar ("yet," "for"). Students at the instructional level might have a limited vocabulary and struggle to use a variety of coordinating conjunctions effectively.

The video developed is entitled "Home Alone" is all about the little girl who was once left alone in their home because her parents have an important meeting. But before they left, they warned their child of not letting somebody get into their house especially if he/ she seems strange. Meanwhile, after a few moments, somebody knocked on the door. The little girl didn't open and immediately rush to call her father to tell what was happening. The father then advised on what to do, to avoid danger. With that circumstance the parents were very proud of the obedience their child manifested.

Based on this story children will identify coordinating conjunctions that will help them improve their skills. In this way they will be able to write/compose their own sentences, paragraphs or even short stories using coordinating Conjunctions.

Evaluate Narratives Based on how the Author Developed the Elements of Plot.

Evaluating narratives based on plot development can be challenging for students at the instructional level. Plot refers to the sequence of events in a story. Instructional level readers might struggle to grasp the concept of a narrative arc, including exposition, rising action, climax, falling action, and resolution. Recognizing key elements like the inciting incident, conflict, character goals, and turning points can be difficult for readers who focus primarily on understanding the literal meaning of the text. Analyzing how the author uses plot elements to create suspense, build tension, or develop characters requires abstract thinking skills that might be underdeveloped at the instructional level.

By adapting this competency and providing support, teachers can help students at the instructional level develop their reading comprehension skills and learn to appreciate how plot contributes to a story's overall effectiveness.

This story video developed is entitled "Androcles and the Lion" it is about the slave who escaped from the palace and met a groaning lion in the middle of the forest. He suddenly ran away but after noticing that the lion did not chase after him he came back to know what was happening. He then saw that the paw of the lion was swelling and bleeding. He decided to help the lion and they became friends. After so many months the king's men found Androcles and the Lion and they decided to bring them back to the palace. As punishment they put Androcles and the Lion in a cage and didn't let the lion eat for how many weeks. When they get loose of the lion it rushed to the victim but when he saw that it was Androcles he did not do any harmful thing to his friend. So, after seeing this, the king decided to bring back the lion and Androcles to the forest. This shows that even animals' values friendship and loyal to his master. It gives moral lesson to our learners that no matter what happen we should always remain loyal despite of all the challenges that we may face in our lives. It gives us idea how importance to other people in our daily life. Even Lion as describe as a terrific animal but still manage to give importance to the one that helped him during his lowest time.

This story will be a great helped learner to sequence the events from what had happen first up to the last. It will be enhanced learners' ability in identifying conflicts of the characters in the story and to find its solution. By means of reading stories like this learner will develop the expected skills to them.

Distinguishing Text Type according to Purpose and Language Features (Cause and Effects).

This competency can be challenging for students at the instructional level because it requires them to analyze the text beyond its literal meaning. Instructional level readers might focus primarily on understanding the content of the text and struggle to identify its overall purpose (to inform, persuade, entertain, etc.). Recognizing how events are connected and how one event leads to another requires a deeper understanding of text structure and logical reasoning. Cause-and-effect texts often use specific signal words like "because," "so," "therefore," "as a result," etc. Students at the instructional level might have limited vocabulary and struggle to identify these cues.

By adapting the competency and providing support through visuals, clear explanations, and engaging activities, teachers can help students at the instructional level develop the skills needed to distinguish text types and identify cause-and-effect relationships within them. This will enhance their overall reading comprehension skills.

The final video developed is entitled “The Lady of the Lamp” it is about Florence Nightingale a young lady whose passion is on nursing even though her parents did not want to, because they wanted her to marry a rich man. Despite the discouragement of her parents still she pursued her ambition and became a good nurse. Her contribution of nursing soldiers during the war is a great help to drop the number of wounded soldiers. Because of her heroic work, Red Cross was established considering Florence as their inspiration. The story could inspire the learners to embody what Florence has exhibited. And it inspires learners to do the same. It simply shows that being a hero is not about having a superpower but being thoughtful, kind, responsible in everything we do

By means of reading this kind of story learners will be able to identify and understand the cause and the effect. When learners always read this kind of stories they will enhance their skills and met the expected skills from them.

Table 3

List of Identified Competencies and Developed Video Reading Material

Competencies	Video Reading Material
Respond appropriately to the messages of the different authentic texts (ENG. RC-IIa – 5.5)	
Recognizing Comparison and Contrast Text (ENG RC-IV-C-15)	

Present a Coherent Comprehensive Report on Differing Viewpoints on an Issue (ENG. OL-IIIh-1.19)

Compose Clear and Coherent Sentences Using Coordinating Conjunctions

Evaluate Narratives Based on how the Author Developed the Elements of Plot (ENG6 RC-Ih-2.243)

Distinguish Text Type according to Purpose and Language Features (Cause and Effects) (ENG RC-Iva-3.2.6)

Qualitative Data Analysis

Learners' Experiences in using the Digital-Based Reading Materials

In this study, three (3) participants out of thirty-eight Grade 6 elementary learners were purposively selected according to the results of the reading comprehension test. They were interviewed to verify their experiences in using the video reading materials. The responses drawn were analyzed using the Thematic Analysis. During the interview, the participants were allowed to use their native language so that they could express their

thoughts confidently. Nevertheless, they tried their best to answer the questions in English Language.

When the participants were asked about their experiences using the digital reading materials, the themes that prevailed in their responses were: it made reading fun and interesting, it improved reading interests and the digital materials enhanced their reading comprehension and vocabulary.

Makes Reading Fun and Interesting

Using Video has revolutionized reading comprehension learning by making it enjoyable, exciting, and enriching. Through its ability to bring texts to life, offering visual context, and sparking enthusiasm for exploration, video enhances comprehension and engages learners in ways that traditional reading alone cannot. As educators and learners embrace the vast array of video resources available in the digital age, they unlock new pathways to understanding, creativity, and lifelong learning. This is one of common knowledge by teachers in every discipline and one of the reasons why videos is commonly used in teaching. This is also being agreed by the participants who have been interviewed by the researcher. By viewing videos, this made reading comprehension learning easy for them since they are more motivated and interested compared to traditional teaching.

According to Learner 1, *“Yes, because as I watch and listen to digital based reading materials it gives me excitement and I enjoy everything.”* Learner is also exited to watch more videos on reading comprehension, *“I’m still interested to watch more videos to enhance my understanding...”* As for Learner 2, *“All the videos that I watched is a great helped, in the time I finished it, my understanding improves. I’m very interested to watch more videos like this in the future”*. (Yes, because it has enhanced my overall learning experiences and I enjoy watching digital reading materials it gives me excitement and improves my reading comprehension skills). Learner 3, *“Yes, because as I watch and listen to digital based reading materials it gives me excitement and I enjoyed everything”*.

According to Celce-Murcia (1991), efficient comprehension requires the ability to relate the textual material to one's own knowledge and the goals of a prereading stage are to activate students' knowledge of a subject, provide any language preparation that might be needed for coping with the passage, and motivating learners to want to read the text, videos can be used to activate their schemata because of involving their auditory and visual senses. Other research also suggests that exposure to digital texts from an early age fosters the development of digital literacy skills, which are essential for navigating and comprehending digital information in the modern world (Wang & Smith, 2021). Brown & Lee (2019) supported that digital materials offer opportunities for personalized learning experiences, allowing students to access texts tailored to their individual reading levels and interests, thereby enhancing comprehension. However, Brown et al.,(2021) firmly believe that the discrepancy between the availability of digital materials and the lack of comprehensive frameworks for evaluating their efficacy underscores the urgent need for standardized protocols in educational research and practice.

It Improved Reading Interest

Digital reading materials play a pivotal role in enhancing reading interest by offering accessibility, diversity, interactivity, and community engagement. In an increasingly digitalized world, these platforms have revolutionized the way we consume literature and informational content, making reading more accessible, engaging, and enriching than ever before. By harnessing the power of technology to connect readers with a wealth of diverse content and interactive experiences, digital reading materials inspire a lifelong love of reading and learning, ensuring that the magic of storytelling continues to captivate and inspire generations to come. This is believed by the learners as they had experienced watching the developed digital reading material. According to Learner 2, "It helped to improved my skills to understand reading materials and I'm still interested to watch more videos to enhance my understanding" As for Learner 3, "Because of watching digital reading materials it helps me in developing my own ability in reading".

As per stated in the Flow Theory (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990), digital reading materials, especially those with interactive features and customizable options, can facilitate flow by providing readers with a challenging yet achievable task that aligns with their skills and interests. When readers experience flow while engaging with digital reading materials, they are more likely to feel a sense of fulfillment and satisfaction, which in turn sustains their interest in reading.

Enhanced Reading Comprehension and Vocabulary

Video reading materials play a vital role in improving comprehension by engaging multiple senses, fostering visual literacy, and promoting active learning. As educators and learners embrace the diverse range of resources available in the digital landscape, integrating video content into educational practices offers unparalleled opportunities to enrich learning experiences and empower individuals to become critical thinkers and lifelong learners. This is also the experience as narrated by the participants. According to Learner 1, "...because it helps me to enhanced and understand more skills in reading, and it helps me to expand my vocabulary". For Learner 2, "It helped to improved my skills to understand reading materials And according to Learner 3, "Because of watching digital reading materials it helps me in developing my own ability in reading".

The statements of the participants are a testament that use video materials for instruction really improved their skills in to reading comprehension. It can be observed from the result that digital reading materials offer opportunities for personalized learning experiences tailored to individual preferences and needs. It also offers multimedia enhancements such as audio narration, visual aids, and interactive simulations, which can enhance comprehension and reinforce vocabulary acquisition. According Draper (2012) Viewing video clips seems to build students' background knowledge and can help them comprehend texts by providing visual images for unusual topics. Besides, visualization has been characterized as a very important prerequisite for a good reader to improve his reading comprehension skill.

Experts' Evaluation of the Acceptability of the Video Reading Materials

In the digital age, evaluating the usability and effectiveness of digital materials becomes imperative to ensure their alignment with pedagogical objectives and to maximize their impact on students' reading comprehension abilities" (Gao et al., 2018). The result coincides with the review of Chen and Wang (2019), in which they found that the quality of digital materials significantly impacted their effectiveness in improving reading comprehension. Thus, there is a need to develop and evaluate high-quality digital materials for reading comprehension. In response to this need, recent research has focused on developing and evaluating digital materials for reading comprehension. For example, a study by Li (2020) developed a digital reading platform with personalized features and assessed its effectiveness in improving reading comprehension among middle school students. Another study by Xiong and Li (2021) investigated the effects of gamification on reading comprehension in a digital learning environment.

Table 4 shows that the level of acceptability of the instructional material across various aspects. Specifically, evaluators rated content quality (M= 3.93, SD= .082), instructional quality (M= 3.90, SD= .126), technical quality (M= 3.92, SD= .097), and other factors (M= 3.83, SD= .204) as highly acceptable. This simply showed that can be used as instructional materials in improving the reading comprehension of the learners since it has been evaluated as highly acceptable.

While the proliferation of digital resources for reading comprehension is evident, the absence of robust methodologies for assessing their quality and instructional value contributes to a notable gap in the educational technology literature." (Garcia et al., 2019). The gap between the development and evaluation of digital materials for reading comprehension suggests a critical area for future research and policy intervention to ensure the alignment of educational technology with pedagogical goals and student learning outcomes (Johnson & Lee, 2017).

Table 4

The Level of Acceptability of the Instructional Materials in Terms of Content Quality, Instructional Quality, Technical Quality and Others

Variable	Mean	SD	Description
Content quality	3.93	.082	Highly acceptable
Instructional quality	3.90	.126	Highly acceptable
Technical Quality	3.92	.097	Highly acceptable
Others	3.83	.204	Highly acceptable

Scale:

Mean	Description
3.26 – 4.00	Highly acceptable
2.51 – 3.25	Acceptable
1.76 – 2.50	Less acceptable
1.00 – 1.75	Not acceptable

Conclusions

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the potential of video-based digital reading materials to improve reading comprehension among elementary learners.

The baseline assessment revealed that the target learners primarily demonstrated an instructional reading level. This highlights the need for targeted instruction and support to enhance their ability to comprehend and process complex texts. This information can be used to develop a differentiated instructional plan that addresses specific needs. Such a plan may incorporate digital reading materials, focus on skills like identifying comparison and contrast elements, and utilize graphic organizers to support understanding.

Analysis of the video reading materials suggests their design aligns with the intended goal of enhancing students' comprehension and analytical skills. The videos likely focus on improving understanding of different text types (including comparative and contrasting texts) and the messages they convey. While elements like clear sentence structure and narrative elements might be present, the core objective appears to be building comprehension and analytical capabilities across diverse content sources.

Furthermore, the learner experiences suggest that the video materials were successful in increasing reading engagement and motivation among students. This ultimately led to improvements in reading comprehension and vocabulary development.

Finally, the expert assessment indicates a high standard of acceptability for the video reading materials across various aspects. This includes the content's accuracy, relevance, and alignment with learning objectives; the instructional design's effectiveness in delivering content and engaging learners; and the technical quality of video and audio clarity, user-friendliness. This positive evaluation suggests significant potential for the video materials to serve as a valuable tool for enhancing students' reading comprehension skills.

Recommendations

This study investigated the potential of video-based digital reading materials to enhance reading comprehension among elementary learners. The findings offer valuable insights for various stakeholders in the area of education.

This study's findings can inform curriculum developers in designing engaging and effective learning materials. Textbooks can be enhanced by incorporating complementary video resources and instructional materials aligned with the videos' content. This integrated approach can foster a deeper understanding of various language skills, particularly reading comprehension.

The research highlights the potential of technology to support and revise teaching practices. Teachers and practitioners can consider using video reading materials

alongside traditional written texts. These videos can serve as a valuable supplement to written materials, enhancing engagement and comprehension. However, it's crucial to maintain a balance – video materials should complement, not replace, written texts.

Parents play a crucial role in supporting their children's learning journey. This study suggests that parents can encourage active engagement with video content. Strategies include pausing the video to ask questions, summarize key points, or connect the content to personal experiences. Additionally, creating a conducive learning environment at home, with a quiet and comfortable space for watching videos and completing related activities, can further enhance the learning experience. Parents can actively participate in their children's learning by showing interest in the video reading materials they are using. Asking about their progress, offering support, and providing encouragement can significantly benefit a child's learning journey.

Lastly, further research along this line is recommended to validate the study's findings across diverse contexts and learner populations. Future studies could explore the long-term impact of video-based reading materials and investigate their effectiveness in developing other language skills beyond reading comprehension.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study took into consideration the ethical standards in doing research. Primarily the research respondents were fully informed about the procedures involved in research and must give their consent to participate. Ethical standards also required the researcher to ensure the privacy and confidentiality of the subject being studied. Two standards applied in order to protect the privacy of the research participants. Almost all research guarantees the participants' confidentiality -- they were assured that identifying information would not be made available to anyone who is not directly involved in the study. The stricter standard is the principle of anonymity which essentially means that the participant should remain anonymous throughout the study.

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